

A NOVEL DESIGN OF INJECTABLE POROUS HYDROGELS WITH *IN SITU* PORE FORMATION

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ABSTRACT

The use of injectable porous hydrogels is of great interest in biomedical applications due to their excellent permeability and ease of integration into sites of surgical intervention. By implementing a method that enables the formation of the pores *in situ* with controllable porosity and pore size, it is possible to synthesize bioactive hydrogels that are tailor-made for specific biomedical applications. An emulsion-templating technique was used to encapsulate oil droplets, which are subsequently leached out of the hydrogel to create the porous structure. Pore size and porosity were manipulated by changing oil-to-water ratios and the surfactant concentrations. Highly swellable porous hydrogels were obtained with control over mechanical strength and diffusive properties. The relationship between porosity, pore size, and the hydrogel's physical and mechanical characteristics was analyzed, and the potential of this material as a protein drug delivery system was demonstrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Porous hydrogels have been widely studied in the recent years. Several classes of porous hydrogels were described in the literature. Superporous hydrogels (SPHs) and superabsorbent polymers (SAPs) are a class of structurally cross-linked hydrophilic polymers, which have the ability to absorb extensive quantities of water or aqueous fluids (10–1000 times their original weight or volume) in relatively short periods of time [1, 2]. These hydrogels may be prepared using freeze-drying [3], porogenesis [4, 5], microemulsion formation [6], phase separation [7] and a gas blowing technique which involves the decomposition of bicarbonate [8]. Another class of porous hydrogels is cryogels, which are macroporous hydrogels formed below the melting point of the solvent [9, 10]. Porous hydrogels are useful in various biomedical applications such as tissue engineering and *in vitro* cell culture. Control over the porous structure is achieved through the size and volume of microspheres inserted [11, 12], the monomer ratio [13-15], the choice of porogen [16, 17], the pressure and formation temperatures in freeze-drying and sphere templating techniques [16, 18-20], the volume of CO₂ in gas foaming [16], the size of salt crystals in particle leaching [21], and the surfactant concentration and template volume in emulsion-templating [22].

Injectable hydrogels have emerged as favorable biomaterials because of their excellent permeability and ease of integration in surgical procedures using less invasive approaches. Due to their unique characteristics, they can be used to administer bioactive agents such as proteins, genes, and living cells. Hydrogels have relatively high water content (>90 wt%) resulting in an aqueous environment favorable for preserving the native structure and bioactivity of proteins. The highly porous structure of hydrogels enables them to carry large quantities of protein drugs. This feature is a basic characteristic for developing long-term protein delivery systems that are able to provide continuous protein release. Lastly, proteins can be incorporated within a gel matrix under mild conditions (e.g. physiological temperature and pH) that are not harmful to proteins [23]. Because of these advantages, they have been explored for protein drug delivery and tissue engineering applications [23-28].

Biomaterials that are both injectable and porous may offer even more possibilities in the areas of bioactive delivery and regenerative medicine. In particular, porosity can be critically important when cell infiltration or nutrient supply is required in the bulk of the scaffold. Nevertheless, many of the current techniques for creating porosity cannot be applied to injectable hydrogels since they use cytotoxic materials in the preparation stages and/or aggressive methods for porogen extraction. Several attempts to induce a porous structure in injectable hydrogels have been described in the literature [29-34]. However, all these studies employed a freeze-drying technique that eliminates any possibility of injecting the hydrogel afterwards. An injectable, *in situ* forming biodegradable gel consisting of chitosan, glycerol phosphate (GP) and oxidized hyaluronic acid was synthesized for tissue engineering applications [29]. The porosity was controlled through variation in the degree of oxidation. Another research reported on a new injectable and *in situ* crosslinked hydrogel, based on a hyaluronic acid (HA) derivative and a,b-polyaspartylhydrazide (PAHy) with a controlled pore size attained by adjusting pH and ionic strength [30]. An injectable hydrogel for localized drug delivery was prepared from Hydrazine and aldehyde modified poly(aspartic acids) [31]. The porous structure was manipulated by altering the crosslinking degree of the two gel precursors. Another injectable chitosan-based thermosensitive hydrogel was used for insulin sustained drug delivery [32]. An injectable thermo-sensitive composite hydrogel composed of polyethylene glycol – polycaprolactone-polyethylene glycol (PEG-PCL-PEG) copolymer, collagen and HA was used for bone regeneration purposes [33]. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) micrographs demonstrated an interconnected porous structure, which helped to facilitate better tissue regeneration. Another study recently reported the synthesis of macroporous alginate gels used as a minimally invasive bulking agent [34]. The hydrogel's porosity, 98%, was created by freeze-drying with pore morphologies and sizes manipulated through the processing temperature and time.

The aim of the current research was to develop a method for fabricating compatible and bioactive hydrogels that are both porous and injectable. We based our hydrogel design on an oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion-templating technique used to encapsulate droplets of biocompatible oil (stabilized with a non-toxic surfactant) within cross-linkable polymer precursor solution [35]. The emulsion, which contains the precursor solution, can be crosslinked by non-toxic light-activated polymerization after injection into the body. Finally, the droplets are leached out to form pores *in situ*, as depicted in Fig. 1. Injectable non-porous PEG-Fibrinogen (PF) hydrogels were previously shown to be applicable in an *in situ* tissue engineering approach for myocardial repair in rats and skeletal-muscle disorders [36, 37]. We report on the application of this newly developed technique to create porous bioactive PF hydrogels. Manipulating pore size and porosity was achieved by utilizing different surfactant concentrations and varying oil-to-water ratios. The porous PF hydrogels were characterized by swelling and mechanical strength experiments, droplet size analysis, and gravimetric oil extraction. High Resolution Scanning Electron Microscopy (HR-SEM) was used to study the hydrogel's porous structure, and protein diffusion experiments were conducted in order to demonstrate the material's diffusivity and potential for sustained drug delivery. In addition, cytotoxicity assessments were performed in order to evaluate the compatibility of the hydrogel's precursor constituents with living cells. Finally, the relationship between structure and physical and mechanical properties was investigated. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of the formation of an injectable, biodegradable, and bioactive hydrogel exhibiting surface and bulk porosity with pore formation occurring *in situ* by an emulsion-templating technique. The design of such biomedical

hydrogels that are both porous and injectable could open the door to a new generation of clinically applied biomaterials.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation of PEG-fibrinogen (PF) precursor solution

PEG-fibrinogen was prepared according to the method described elsewhere [38]. Briefly, bovine plasma fibrinogen (Sigma-Aldrich) was dissolved in 130 mM phosphate buffer saline (PBS) containing 8M Urea to a final concentration of 8.5 ± 0.5 mg/ml. Tris (2-carboxyethyl) phosphine hydrochloride (TCEP) (Sigma-Aldrich) was added to completely dissolve the protein at a molar ratio of 1.5:1 TCEP to fibrinogen. After dissolution, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 8 using 1 M NaOH solution and a solution of polyethylene glycol diacrylate (PEG-DA) (280 mg ml⁻¹) in 130 mM PBS with 8 M urea was added and reacted for 3 h at room temperature in the dark. After the reaction was completed, the PEGylated protein was diluted 1:1 with 130 mM PBS containing 8 M urea and precipitated by adding four volumes of acetone at room temperature in a separation funnel. The precipitate was redissolved, homogenized and dialyzed against 130 mM PBS at 4°C for 24 h with two changes of PBS (Spectrum, 12–14 kDa mol. wt. cutoff). Protein concentration was determined by Bis-Cinchoninic Acid (BCA) protein assay.

2.2 Emulsion-templated PF hydrogels

Emulsion-templated PF hydrogels were prepared at different concentrations of O/W emulsions. Briefly, 3%, 7%, or 10% (w/v) Pluronic[®]F68 was added to 50%, 75% or 95% (v/v) PF precursor solution (protein concentration 8.5 ± 0.5 mg/ml) at 4°C in 20 ml glass vial until complete dissolution of the surfactant was achieved. The solution was mixed with 0.1% (v/v) photoinitiator stock solution (10% (w/v) Irgacure[®]2959 in 70% ethanol and 30% deionized water). Paraffin oil (5%, 25%, or 50%, v/v) was added drop wise to the solution under constant stirring to a final emulsion volume of 2.5 ml. Stirring was continued for 15 min after the oil was added. The mixing time was kept constant in order to reduce emulsion inhomogeneity. Two stirring devices were used: a magnetic stirrer and an overhead mechanical stirrer. The overhead mechanical stirrer was comprised of a propeller at the diameter of 1.5 cm rotating at an angular velocity of 1950 rpm. Finally, the emulsion was irradiated with UV light (365nm, 4-5 mW/m²) for 5 min in order to achieve chemical crosslinking of the hydrogel.

2.3 Cell culture and cytotoxicity

Emulsion solutions were prepared with culture medium DMEM instead of PF. Neonatal human dermal fibroblasts (HDFs) culture preparation is described elsewhere [39]. The HDFs were sub-cultured in flat-bottom 48 well tissue culture plates with an initial cell density of around 40,000 cells per well and 550 μ l DMEM culture medium. Cells were cultured and incubated in a temperature-controlled CO₂ incubator. The medium was replaced with emulsion solutions after an initial 24 hr incubation, followed by an additional overnight incubation. Cell viability was assessed using a calcein and ethidium homodimer live/dead viability assay (Sigma Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Stained cells were visualized using a Nikon TS100 fluorescence microscope and imaged with a Nikon Digital Sight DS-SMc for further analysis. Live cells were stained positive with green fluorescence, while dead cells were visualized by red-stained nuclei. The red and green images were superimposed to yield the final live/dead results.

2.4 Cell - seeded constructs

Cell seeded porous hydrogels were prepared by crosslinking the emulsion solutions in a cylindrical mold with an inner diameter of 2 mm. The solutions contained PF (protein concentration 8.5 ± 0.5 mg/ml) and HDFs (cell density of 500,000 cells/ml). Following crosslinking under long wave UV light for 5 min, the resulting hydrogels were transferred to a flat bottom 48-well culture dish containing 1.5 ml of DMEM culture medium. The cultures were incubated at 37°C in a temperature-controlled CO₂ incubator and monitored for a week. The culture medium was replaced every day. Control hydrogels, with no porosity, were prepared and cultured in a similar manner but without the emulsion, as described elsewhere [39].

2.5 Oil droplet diameter determination

The average diameter of oil droplets embedded in the emulsion-templated PF hydrogels immediately after cross-linking and after reaching equilibrium swelling (i.e. fully hydrated) was

analyzed by phase contrast-enhanced light microscopy. In order to prepare hydrogel samples, 60 μl of emulsion (as described in section 2.2) were transferred to a plastic mold having a thickness of 2 mm. The sample was then cross-linked by long-wave UV photo-polymerization, removed from the mold and placed on a glass slide. The resulting hydrogels were thin enough to allow visualization of the encapsulated oil droplets using the optical microscope system. Image analysis of digital phase-contrast micrographs was performed by NIH ImageJ 1.42q software (National Institutes of health, USA). The average cross sectional area of the oil droplets was calculated based on measurements of 100 droplets. The average diameter of oil droplet was defined as:

$$d_{oil} = \sqrt{\frac{4 \cdot S_{oil}}{\pi}} \quad (1)$$

where d_{oil} is the average oil droplet diameter and S_{oil} is the average droplet's cross sectional area. In the analysis used to calculate the average oil droplet size (Fig. 3J), the data points represent the percentage from total emulsion composition rather than the percentage from PF phase.

2.6 HR-SEM analysis

Pore size and porosity of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels, prepared at different Oil-to-PF ratios and surfactant concentrations, were characterized using HR-SEM. Samples for HR-SEM experiments were prepared by submerging the emulsion-templated PF hydrogels in double distilled water for 24 hr to induce the extraction of internal droplet phase. In order to extract oil remaining residues, the PF hydrogels were subsequently submerged in acetone for another 24 hr, followed by freeze-drying. Cross sections of the samples were tested at a very low electron acceleration voltage of 1-4kV and a working distance of 3-5nm for high resolution imaging of surface structures. A Zeiss Ultra Plus HR-SEM equipped with a Schotkky field-emission electron gun was used. Specific imaging detectors were chosen accordingly.

2.7 Liquid displacement method

Liquid displacement method [40] was used to calculate the overall porosity of the hydrogels. Sample hydrogels were prepared the same as described in section 2.6. Each sample of about 20 mg was immersed in a 5 ml pycnometer containing a known volume V_1 of a displacement liquid. The sample was held in the displacement liquid for 5 min, followed by a series of brief evacuation–repressurization cycles in order to force the displacement liquid into the pores of the material. The total volume of the displacement liquid and the displacement liquid-impregnated material were referred to as V_2 . The volume difference ($V_2 - V_1$) was taken as the volume of the skeleton of the material. The liquid-impregnated hydrogel was then removed from the pycnometer, and the residual displacement liquid volume was taken as V_3 . Consequently, the total volume of the material is:

$$V = (V_2 - V_1) + (V_1 - V_3) \quad (2)$$

The porosity of the material is expressed by:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{(V_1 - V_3)}{(V_2 - V_3)} \quad (3)$$

The porosity of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels at different concentrations after oil extraction was determined by the liquid displacement method using ethanol as the displacement liquid.

2.8 Gravimetric oil extraction

The internal droplet phase was leached from the hydrogel to obtain a porous matrix. Hydrogel samples were placed in 10 ml glass vials and were submerged in double distilled water with a volume 15 times greater than that of the internal droplet phase. Leaching proceeded for up to one week with daily replacement of the water. The samples were withdrawn from the extracting solution at days 1, 4 and 7, and placed in a heating oven (WTC binder, Germany) at 70°C until all double distilled water was fully evaporated. The aggregate amount of oil and surfactants extracted were calculated according to the following mass balance:

$$\% \text{ oil extracted} = \left(\frac{w_{dry}}{(w_{surfactant} + w_{oil})} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

where W_{dry} is the weight of the oil and surfactant remaining after water evaporation, $W_{surfactant}$ is the initial surfactant weight, and W_{oil} is the initial oil weight.

2.9 Swelling experiments

The swelling ability of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels at different Oil-to-PF ratios, and different surfactant concentrations were studied as a function of time. The results were compared to control PF hydrogels using the same experimental setup which was previously described [39]. The swelling ratio was determined gravimetrically as follows:

$$Q = \frac{(m_w - m_D)}{m_w} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

where m_w is the weight of the swollen hydrogel minus the amount of internal droplet phase extracted, and m_D is the weight of the hydrogel immediately after casting minus the amount of the internal droplet phase extracted.

2.10 Mechanical characterization

A Lloyd mechanical testing machine was used to determine the hydrogel's Young's modulus (E), defined as:

$$E = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

where σ is the stress applied on the sample, and ε is the strain in the linear region of the stress-strain curve. In practice, the Young's modulus was experimentally determined by measuring the slope of the compressive stress-strain curve in the linear region. Sample preparation was the same as described for the swelling experiments, but without submerging the samples in liquid after the photopolymerization. The samples were compressed at a rate of 0.2 mm/min with a compressive displacement of up to 2 mm. The initial length of the sample was determined by recording the location of the sample holders at the zero strain, which is the initial point at which the force values start to increase during compressive loading. The Young's modulus was calculated from the linear region of the stress-strain curve, as the slope between 1%-10% strain [41].

2.11 Protein release experiments

Lysozyme was used as a model protein for release experiments. The lysozyme (10 mg/ml) was added to the emulsion solutions at different Oil-to-PF ratios, and different surfactant concentrations. Hydrogels containing lysozyme were prepared the same as described for the swelling experiments, but were submerged in 20 ml 130 mM PBS in plastic vials. They were subsequently transferred to a shaking bath at room temperature (frequency set at 100 rpm). Samples of 0.5 ml PBS were withdrawn at each time interval and replaced with fresh PBS. Samples were collected for further protein concentration determination after 48 hr.

2.12 Determination of protein concentration

Protein concentration was determined using the Folin–Ciocalteu method [42], as was previously described in detail [43]. The intensity of the resulting blue color was measured in a TECAN infinite M200 PRO plate reader (NEOTEC) at a wavelength of 750 nm. Absorbance was translated to concentration using a standard calibration curve.

2.13 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft[®] Excel software. Data from independent experiments were quantified and analyzed for each variable. Comparisons between multiple treatments were made with analysis of variance (ANOVA), and ad-hoc comparisons between two treatments were made using a one-tail student's t-test. A p-value of <0.05 was considered to be statistically significant. Standard errors of the mean (SEM) were calculated and presented for each treatment group.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Preparation of porous injectable hydrogels

The current research details a novel method for the creation of injectable porous biocompatible hydrogels with *in situ* pore formation. This method is based on an O/W emulsion-templating technique which is used for encapsulating oil droplets within a crosslinkable precursor solution and subsequently photo-crosslinking the solution by long wave UV light irradiation. The droplets are then leached out of the hydrogel by diffusion upon submerging in an aqueous environment, resulting in a porous hydrogel with pores similar in dimensions to the initial oil droplets (illustrated in Fig. 1). In initial testing, two stirring methods were evaluated as options for forming the O/W emulsions: a magnetic stirrer and an overhead mechanical stirrer. In order to determine the best option for stirring, the hydrogels were formed from PF precursor solution using either method, and two parameters were measured: the percent extracted oil and the size of oil droplets. The results demonstrated that the magnetic stirrer method did not yield reproducible or reliable outcomes. In contrast, the overhead mechanical stirrer enabled tunable pore size and porosity due to its constant and measurable frequency and homogeneous stirring features. The overhead mechanical stirrer was thus chosen as the standard method for all further experiments.

Figure 1: A schematic illustration depicting the preparation of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels.

3.2 Cytotoxicity assays

The cytotoxicity of the system's components was investigated using a standard cytotoxicity evaluation. HDFs were cultured in the presence of the emulsion components, and results showed high viability for all treatments, including with an oil/DMEM ratio of 10% oil and 90% DMEM, as well as with 5% to 15% surfactant concentrations (Fig. 2A-2B), which is in accordance with studies reported in the literature on the cytotoxicity of paraffin oil to cells [44-46]. Therefore, we concluded that surfactant concentrations lower than 15% can be safely used without inducing cytotoxic effects. Additional experiments demonstrating survival of HDFs within 3D hydrogels after the cell-seeded constructs were formed by emulsion templating was further evidence of the non-toxicity of this *in situ* process. Extensive cell spreading was evident in the 10%Pluronic®F68 hydrogels that were formed with cells *in situ* using an emulsion of 5%Oil/95%PF (Fig. 2C-2D).

Figure 2: Human dermal fibroblast viability in PF solutions containing 10%Oil/90%DMEM emulsion with 5%Pluronic[®]F68 (A) and 15%Pluronic[®]F68 (B). Human dermal fibroblast morphology in PF 3D constructs containing 10%Pluronic[®]F68 emulsion-templated with 5%Oil/95%PF (C) and (D).

3.3 Morphological characterization and size analysis

Micrographs of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels made from different compositions were captured by contrast-enhanced light microscopy immediately after photopolymerization in order to study microstructure. As expected, a lower density of oil droplets was observed in hydrogels with lower Oil-to-PF ratios. Moreover, the diameter of the oil droplets decreased with an increase in surfactant concentration for each of the emulsion compositions tested (Fig. 3A-3I). In order to quantify the relationship between oil droplet diameter and surfactant concentration, a statistical size analysis was performed for hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization as well as for hydrogels that are fully hydrated after overnight incubation in PBS. A correlation was found between the droplet diameter and the surfactant percentage from emulsion; for surfactant concentrations at the range of 0% to 4%, droplet diameter decreases linearly with the increase in surfactant concentration, regardless of emulsion composition (Fig. 3J). Nevertheless, at higher surfactant concentrations, this dependence is less significant. Another observation that was evident from this data is that fully hydrated hydrogels contained significantly smaller droplets compared to hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization.

Figure 3: Phase-contrast enhanced light micrographs of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels (immediately following photopolymerization) made from 5%Oil/95%PF (A-C), 25%Oil/75%PF (D-F) and 50%Oil/50%PF (G-I). Three different surfactant concentrations were used: 3%Pluronic®F68 (A, D, G), 7% Pluronic®F68 (B, E, H) and 10% Pluronic®F68 (C, F, I). Quantitative analysis of the oil droplet diameter versus surfactant percentage from emulsions are shown for emulsion-templated PF hydrogels (fully hydrated and immediately after photopolymerization) made from: (■)5%Oil/95%PF, (◆)25%Oil/75%PF, and (▲)50%Oil/50%PF.

HR-SEM is a common technique for observing hydrogel porosity and pore size [47, 48]. Micrographs from HR-SEM studies were obtained in order to study the porosity after freeze-drying, whereby all of the internal droplet phase is leached out. Comparing micrographs of emulsion-templated hydrogels to the control hydrogels was used to ascertain the effects associated with the emulsion-templating technique, because structural changes resulting from freeze-drying affect all samples in a similar manner. Consequently, the HR-SEM data provides a means of qualitatively evaluating the relationship between oil droplet diameter and final pore size in the hydrogel. Higher porosity was detected at higher oil concentrations (Fig. 4B-4D), suggesting that hydrogel porosity could be fine-tuned using the emulsion composition parameter. Generally, a rough assessment of pore diameters showed that pore sizes were in the range of 5-50 μm , which is similar to the range of oil droplet diameters measured prior to oil extraction. The control hydrogels, without an emulsion

templating, appeared much more uniform with only a few pores visible, which could be artifacts of the freeze-drying process (Fig. 4A). Some interconnections between pores can be observed at higher oil concentrations (Fig. 4D).

Figure 4: HR-SEM micrographs of PF hydrogels. Shown are representative samples of controls made without emulsion-templating (A), emulsion-templated hydrogels made from 5%Oil/95%PF (B), 25%Oil/75%PF (C) and 50%Oil/50%PF (D), all containing 10%Pluronic[®]F68.

3.4 Gravimetric oil extraction

In the current system, the extraction of the droplet phase dictates the *in situ* porosity potential of the hydrogel. Therefore, the extraction of internal droplet phase (oil and surfactant) was measured gravimetrically. The amount of the internal droplet phase extracted from the hydrogels was high in the first 24 hr, followed by a slower extraction over a period of one week (see supplementary material, Fig. S1). Higher amounts of the internal droplet phase are extracted in hydrogels which initially contained larger concentrations of oil and higher surfactant percentages (Fig. 5A). Normalizing this data by calculating the percentage of internal droplet phase extracted from the hydrogels shows that when the oil content is high, the percentage of the internal droplet phase that diffuses out of the hydrogel is lower (Fig. 5B).

Figure 5: The effect of surfactant concentration on the amount (A) and percent (B) of internal droplet phase (oil + surfactant) extracted from the PF phase of emulsion-templated hydrogels made with 5%Oil/95%PF (---), 25%Oil/75%PF (...) and 50%Oil/50%PF (□).

3.5 Porosity

Porosity analysis was performed only on hydrogels with the highest mechanical strength (5%Oil/95%PF) because the hydrogels made with 50%Oil/50%PF and 25%Oil/75%PF were very fragile after freeze-drying. Porosity of the 5%Oil/95%PF hydrogels increased with increasing surfactant concentrations (Fig. 6). For all emulsion-templated samples, the porosity was higher than that of the control hydrogels. In order to differentiate between the pores were formed during the freeze drying process. In an attempt to separate the effect of emulsion-templating from that of the drying, the relative porosity was defined as the difference between sample's porosity and the porosity of the control. The relative porosity increases with increasing surfactant percentages (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Absolute porosity (□) and relative porosity (■) of hydrogels emulsion-templated with 5%Oil/95%PF at different surfactant concentrations. The solid line represents the absolute porosity of the control hydrogel samples, and (*), (**) refers to statistically significant porosity ($p < 0.05$).

3.6 Swelling properties

Swelling kinetics of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels were evaluated in order to learn about the physical characteristics of the hydrogels. Higher swelling ($Q = 70\% - 120\%$) was observed for hydrogels with lower oil content at all surfactant concentrations (Fig. 7A-7C). In addition, equilibrium swelling which results in full hydration is reached after 24 hr for all hydrogels tested. The decrease in swelling after 24 hr may be artifactual due to the diffusion of oil droplets out of the hydrogel. Equilibrium swelling as a function of surfactant concentration and oil content was plotted for all hydrogel samples (Fig. 7D). Hydrogels with lower oil content exhibited higher equilibrium swelling at every surfactant concentration, in accordance with the trend observed for swelling kinetics (ANOVA, $p < 0.01$, $n \geq 3$). Moreover, higher equilibrium swelling is observed at higher surfactant concentrations for each of the emulsion compositions (ANOVA, $p < 0.01$, $n \geq 3$), with exceptions being hydrogels comprised of 10%Pluronic[®]F68, emulsion-templated with 50%Oil/50%PF and 25%Oil/75%PF. Generally, the emulsion-templated hydrogels displayed higher equilibrium swelling compared to the controls, which exhibited an equilibrium swelling of 45%; the two exceptions being hydrogels containing 50%Oil/50%PF with 10% and 3% Pluronic[®]F68.

Figure 7: The swelling of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels. Swelling kinetics of hydrogels made with 5%Oil/95%PF (■), 25%Oil/75%PF (◆) and 50%Oil/50%PF (▲) containing 10%Pluronic[®]F68 (A), 7%Pluronic[®]F68 (B) and 3%Pluronic[®]F68 (C). The equilibrium swelling as a function of surfactant concentration from the PF phase is shown for emulsion-templated hydrogels made with 5%Oil/95%PF (---), 25%Oil/75%PF (...), 50%Oil/50%PF (□). The solid line represents the swelling of the control hydrogel samples.

3.7 Mechanical characterization

In order to evaluate the mechanical properties of the emulsion-templated PF hydrogels, the Young's modulus was evaluated immediately after photopolymerization and after equilibrium swelling. Hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization exhibited a lower Young's modulus as a function of lower surfactant percentage and oil concentration (ANOVA, $p < 0.036$, $n \geq 3$) (Fig. 8A). In general, the emulsion-templated hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization and at equilibrium swelling showed lower Young's modulus values compared to the control; the exception being emulsion-templated hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization with 5%Oil/95%PF and 3%Pluronic[®]F68 (Fig. 8A-8B). The fully hydrated hydrogels displayed the opposite trend; higher oil content resulted in higher Young's modulus values (ANOVA, $p < 0.038$, $n \geq 3$) (Fig. 8B). No correlation was found between surfactant concentration and Young's modulus.

Figure 8: The mechanical properties of emulsion-templated PF hydrogels. Young's modulus as a function of surfactant percentage from PF phase is shown for emulsion-templated hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization (A) and fully hydrated hydrogels (B) made with 5%Oil/95%PF (---), 25%Oil/75%PF (...), 50%Oil/50%PF (□). The solid line represents the Young's modulus of the control hydrogels.

3.8 Diffusion experiments and protein release potential

Bioactive protein release from the hydrogels was investigated in the context of controlled delivery applications. Lysozyme was used as a model protein for the release study. Fickian diffusion of a solute from a monolith for short times ($M_t / M_\infty < 0.6$) is described by the following equation [49, 50]:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 4 \left[\frac{Dt}{\pi\delta^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where M_t is the mass of protein released at time t , M_∞ is the mass released at equilibrium, D is the diffusion coefficient, and 2δ is the hydrogel thickness. In a diffusional transport, the fraction of protein released is expected to be proportional to the square root of the release time. The current system should be referred to as a porous monolith; consequently, the diffusion equation has to be adjusted accordingly. Because the porosity of hydrogels is constant, the diffusion equation becomes:

$$\frac{M_t}{M_\infty} = 4 \left[\frac{D_e t}{\pi\delta^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

Where D_e is the effective pore diffusivity which includes the hydrogel's porosity [51].

Lysozyme release profiles from emulsion-templated PF hydrogels, plotted against the square root of the release time, were linear for emulsion-templated hydrogels with 5%Oil/95%PF and 25%Oil/75%PF, at every surfactant concentration (Fig. 9A-9C). Emulsion-templated hydrogels with 50%Oil/50%PF demonstrated a non-diffusive release profile (Fig 9D) which did not fit Eq. 8. Thus, we conclude that a diffusion mechanism is dominant in governing the release of lysozyme out of most of these hydrogels. The effective pore diffusivity of emulsion-templated hydrogels and control hydrogels was calculated as a function of surfactant concentration and emulsion composition (Fig. 9E). Emulsion-templated hydrogels with 50%Oil/50%PF, for which the release profile did not fit Eq. 8, were not evaluated in this manner. Hydrogels with a larger oil content demonstrated higher diffusivity compared to hydrogels with lower oil content and the control hydrogels. Moreover, hydrogels containing 10%Pluronic®F68 exhibited the highest diffusion coefficient.

Figure 9: The release profiles of lysozyme from emulsion-templated PF hydrogels. Lysozyme release kinetics from hydrogels made with 5%Oil/95%PF (■) and 25%Oil/75%PF (◆) containing 10%Pluronic®F68 (A), 7%Pluronic®F68 (B) and 3%Pluronic®F68 (C). (D) The release profile of lysozyme from hydrogel emulsion-templated with 50%Oil/50%PF at 3%Pluronic®F68 (□), 7%Pluronic®F68 (□) and 10%Pluronic®F68 (■). (E) The effective pore diffusivity as a function of surfactant percentage from PF phase is presented for emulsion-templated PF hydrogels with 5%Oil/95%PF (---) and 25%Oil/75%PF (...). The solid line represents the effective pore diffusivity of the control hydrogel, and (*) refers to statistically significant effective pore diffusivity ($p < 0.05$)

compared to emulsion-templated hydrogels with 5%Oil/95%PF (---).

4 DISCUSSION

Manipulating the internal droplet diameter of emulsions is of great importance in controlling pore size in emulsion-templated hydrogels [35]. Droplet size can be fine-tuned by adjusting surfactant concentrations; higher amounts of surfactant increase the availability of the surfactant segments to hydrophobically interact with oil fragments. As a result, the cross sectional area of oil droplets decreases with increasing surfactant concentrations, leading to smaller diameter droplets (Fig. 3J). Moreover, the area-to-volume ratio of larger droplets is smaller; therefore, they are less stable and are more likely to break down or diffuse out as the hydrogel swells. The smaller droplets are more stable, hence they remain encapsulated. This could be one explanation for the observation that fully hydrated emulsion-templated hydrogels can contain smaller oil diameter droplets when compared to emulsion-templated hydrogel immediately after casting. The pore size of the hydrogels can thus be directly controlled by the surfactant concentration, assuming that the dimensions of the hydrogel pores created after oil extraction are proportional to the dimensions of the initially encapsulated oil droplets. However, it is the extraction of the internal droplet phase, together with the size of the droplets, that ultimately dictates the final porosity potential of the hydrogels. It is likely that the oil droplets embedded within the hydrogels are stabilized by a layer of surfactant adsorbed at the oil-aqueous interface. These droplets are extracted from the hydrogel by a diffusion mechanism; higher surfactant and oil concentrations result in larger number of droplets, hence higher levels of internal droplet phase are extracted (Fig. 5A). It is not entirely clear why the calculation of the percentage of internal droplets phase extracted demonstrates that at higher oil content, lower percentage of the internal droplet phase diffuses out of the hydrogel (Fig. 5B). Nevertheless, its practical implications are important because the percentage of the extracted internal droplet phase is expected to determine the *in situ* porosity of the hydrated hydrogels. Indeed, direct porosity measurement demonstrated that for the sample containing 5% oil, porosity increases at higher surfactant concentrations.

The percentage of the extracted internal droplet phase also has a substantial influence on the swelling and the mechanical properties of the hydrogels. The higher swelling ability observed for hydrogels with lower oil content at all surfactant concentrations (Fig. 7A-7C) is attributed to the percent of oil extracted; higher percentage of oil is extracted in hydrogels with lower oil content, which enables water molecules to diffuse into the hydrogel due to osmotic pressure. Moreover, hydrogels initially encapsulated with higher oil content demonstrated higher Young's modulus values (Fig. 8B); this could be attributed to the percent of oil extracted and to the swelling ability. Fully hydrated hydrogels, which displayed higher percentage of oil extracted in emulsions initially prepared with lower oil content, also exhibited higher equilibrium swelling which is known to inversely affect Young's modulus [39]. The correlation between oil droplet size and Young's modulus was also investigated; we hypothesized that the encapsulation of smaller oil droplets, obtained at higher surfactant concentrations, resulted in softer hydrogels; smaller oil droplets, at a constant oil concentration results in a larger total amount of droplets encapsulated in each hydrogel. Because the encapsulation of oil droplets decreases the stiffness, an increase in the amount of encapsulated oil droplets results in diminished Young's modulus values. In addition, the oil's modulus is much smaller than that of the crosslinked network, resulting in a diminished Young's modulus of emulsion-templated hydrogels compared to the control.

Porous injectable hydrogels could be advantageous in the field of protein release which is commonly used in separation processes [52], the delivery of bioactive agents [53], and protein drug delivery [54]. In the broader context of drug delivery, these porous hydrogels are advantageous due to their diffusion-based controlled release profiles. It is well established that the passive diffusion of proteins through porous matrices is enhanced when porosity is increased [55]. In the current hydrogel system, the diffusion of lysozyme is facilitated more readily when prepared with higher oil content. This is likely owing to the higher porosity associated with increased oil concentrations (Fig. 4B-4D). Nevertheless, a non-diffusive mechanism was correlated to one of the reported emulsion-templated hydrogels (50%Oil/50%PF), which exhibited the highest porosity and a partly interconnected pore structure (Fig. 4D). We speculate that a burst release effect dominated the profiles associated with

these particular hydrogels.

In order to better understand the impact of microstructure on the hydrogel's characteristics, various correlations were further investigated. For example, the oil extraction percentage was plotted against the equilibrium swelling (Fig. 10A); for each emulsion composition, higher swelling was linearly correlated with higher percentages of oil extraction, regardless of surfactant concentration. The extraction of oil enabled more water molecules to penetrate into the hydrogel due to osmotic pressure, which resulted in higher equilibrium swelling. The Young's modulus of emulsion-templated hydrogels (immediately after photopolymerization) was plotted against their average droplet diameter (Fig. 10B) to reveal a correlation between modulus and droplet diameter as well as an inverse correlation between modulus and surfactant concentration. The Young's modulus of fully hydrated hydrogels plotted against the percent of oil extracted from the fully hydrated hydrogels reveals an inverse correlation (Fig. 10C). Because the equilibrium swelling of emulsion-templated hydrogels increases at higher percentages of oil extraction, it is only reasonable that the Young's modulus values decrease. In addition, relative porosity values of emulsion-templated hydrogels made with 5%Oil/95%PF were plotted against oil droplet diameter (Fig. 10D), showing that porosity decreases with an increase in droplet diameter. Smaller oil droplets, at similar total oil content, resulted in a higher density of droplets within the hydrogel, which encourages the creation of pores after oil extraction. Finally, we established that droplet size and the percent of oil extracted impacts the pore size and porosity of these hydrogels. Taken together, we speculate that porous injectable hydrogels can be tailor-made for specific biomedical applications by controlling the droplet size and the percent of oil extracted.

Figure 10: Correlation analysis between different hydrogel properties. (A) Equilibrium swelling as a function of percent of oil extracted from fully hydrated hydrogels, (B) Young's modulus as a function of average droplet diameter of hydrogels immediately after photopolymerization, (C) Percent of oil extracted from fully hydrated emulsion-templated PF hydrogels, and (D) Porosity values as a function of oil droplet diameter immediately after photopolymerization of hydrogels made with

5%Oil/95%PF (■), 25%Oil/75%PF (◆) and 50%Oil/50%PF (▲) containing different surfactant concentrations.

5 CONCLUSIONS

A novel method for the synthesis of injectable porous hydrogels with pore formation is presented. This method is based on an O/W emulsion-templating technique which is used for encapsulating oil droplets within a crosslinkable precursor solution, followed by photo-crosslinking with light irradiation. Upon submerging the cross-linked hydrogel in an aqueous environment, the diffusion of the oil droplets out of the hydrogel results in the formation of the porous structure. This structure was nicely controlled by the composition of the hydrogel precursor, which affected both the size of the droplets and their subsequent extraction. The pore structure accordingly affected important properties of the hydrogels, including swelling, Young's modulus and the diffusivity of bioactive molecules in the matrix. Hydrogels with 5%Oil/95%PF and 25%Oil/75%PF compositions were identified as good candidates for drug delivery due to their sustained release profiles of a model protein, lysozyme. Hence, we conclude that by manipulating the structure of the emulsion-templated hydrogels, we can fine-tune certain desirable properties of the material that are required for specific biomedical applications using biocompatible hydrogels.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Chen J, Park H, Park K. Synthesis of superporous hydrogels. Hydrogels with fast swelling and superabsorbent properties. *J Biomed Mater Res* 1999;44:53-62.
- [2] Askari F, Nafisi S, Omidian H, Hashemi SA. Synthesis and characterization of acrylic-based superabsorbents. *J Appl Polym Sci* 1993;50:1851-5.
- [3] Patel VR, Amiji MM. Preparation and characterization of freeze-dried chitosan-poly(ethylene oxide) hydrogels for site-specific antibiotic delivery in the stomach. *Pharm Res* 1996;13:588-93.
- [4] Oxley HR, Corkhill PH, Fitton JH, Tighe BJ. Macroporous hydrogels for biomedical applications: Methodology and morphology. *Biomaterials* 1993;14:1064-72.
- [5] Badiger MV, McNeill ME, Graham NB. Porogens in the preparation of microporous hydrogels based on poly(ethylene oxides). *Biomaterials* 1993;14:1059-63.
- [6] Bennett DJ, Burford RP, Davis TP, Tilley HJ. Synthesis of porous hydrogel structures by polymerizing the continuous phase of a microemulsion. *Polym Int* 1995;36:219-26.
- [7] Chirila TV, Constable IJ, Crawford GJ, Vijayasekaran S, Thompson DE, Chen YC, et al. Poly(2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate) sponges as implant materials: In vivo and in vitro evaluation of cellular invasion. *Biomaterials* 1993;14:26-38.
- [8] Kabiri K, Omidian H, Zohuriaan-Mehr MJ. Novel approach to highly porous superabsorbent hydrogels: synergistic effect of porogens on porosity and swelling rate. *Polym Int* 2003;52:1158-64.
- [9] Henderson TMA, Ladewig K, Haylock DN, McLean KM, O'Connor AJ. Cryogels for biomedical applications. *J Mater Chem B* 2013;1:2682-95.
- [10] Candelaria SL, Chen R, Jeong Y-H, Cao G. Highly porous chemically modified carbon cryogels and their coherent nanocomposites for energy applications. *Energy Environ Sci* 2012;5:5619-37.

- [11] Scholten PM, Ng KW, Joh K, Serino LP, Warren RF, Torzilli PA, et al. A semi-degradable composite scaffold for articular cartilage defects. *J Biomed Mater Res, Part A* 2011;97A:8-15.
- [12] Hwang CM, Sant S, Masaeli M, Kachouie NN, Zamanian B, Lee S-H, et al. Fabrication of three-dimensional porous cell-laden hydrogel for tissue engineering. *Biofabrication* 2010;2:035003/1-12.
- [13] Dang QF, Yan JQ, Li JJ, Cheng XJ, Liu CS, Chen XG. Controlled gelation temperature, pore diameter and degradation of a highly porous chitosan-based hydrogel. *Carbohydr Polym* 2011;83:171-8.
- [14] Spiller KL, Holloway JL, Gribb ME, Lowman AM. Design of semi-degradable hydrogels based on poly(vinyl alcohol) and poly(lactic-co-glycolic acid) for cartilage tissue engineering. *J Tissue Eng Regen Med* 2011;5:636-47.
- [15] Wu W, Liu J, Cao S, Tan H, Li J, Xu F, et al. Drug release behaviors of a pH sensitive semi-interpenetrating polymer network hydrogel composed of poly(vinyl alcohol) and star poly[2-(dimethylamino)ethyl methacrylate]. *Int J Pharm* 2011;416:104-9.
- [16] Annabi N, Nichol JW, Zhong X, Ji C, Koshy S, Khademhosseini A, et al. Controlling the Porosity and Microarchitecture of Hydrogels for Tissue Engineering. *Tissue Eng, Part B* 2010;16:371-83.
- [17] Wachiralarpphaithoon C, Iwasaki Y, Akiyoshi K. Enzyme-degradable phosphorylcholine porous hydrogels cross-linked with polyphosphoesters for cell matrices. *Biomaterials* 2006;28:984-93.
- [18] Galperin A, Long TJ, Ratner BD. Degradable, thermo-sensitive poly(N-isopropyl acrylamide)-based scaffolds with controlled porosity for tissue engineering applications. *Biomacromolecules* 2010;11:2583-2592.
- [19] Kang H-W, Tabata Y, Ikada Y. Fabrication of porous gelatin scaffolds for tissue engineering. *Biomaterials* 1999;20:1339-44.
- [20] Autissier A, Le Visage C, Pouzet C, Chaubet F, Letourneur D. Fabrication of porous polysaccharide-based scaffolds using a combined freeze-drying/cross-linking process. *Acta Biomater* 2010;6:3640-8.
- [21] Chiu Y-C, Larson JC, Isom Jr A, Brey EM. Generation of Porous Poly(Ethylene Glycol) Hydrogels by Salt Leaching. *Tissue Eng, Part C* 2010;16:905-12.
- [22] Zhang J-T, Petersen S, Thunga M, Leipold E, Weidisch R, Liu X, et al. Micro-structured smart hydrogels with enhanced protein loading and release efficiency. *Acta Biomater* 2010;6:1297-306.
- [23] Bae KH, Wang L-S, Kurisawa M. Injectable biodegradable hydrogels: progress and challenges. *J Mater Chem B* 2013;1:5371-88.
- [24] Vermonden T, Censi R, Hennink WE. Hydrogels for Protein Delivery. *Chem Rev* 2012;112:2853-88.
- [25] Censi R, Di Martino P, Vermonden T, Hennink WE. Hydrogels for protein delivery in tissue engineering. *J Controlled Release* 2012;161:680-92.
- [26] Gumusderelioglu M, Erce D, Demirtas TT. Superporous polyacrylate/chitosan IPN hydrogels for protein delivery. *J Mater Sci: Mater Med* 2011;22:2467-75.
- [27] Choh S-Y, Cross D, Wang C. Facile Synthesis and Characterization of Disulfide-Cross-Linked Hyaluronic Acid Hydrogels for Protein Delivery and Cell Encapsulation. *Biomacromolecules* 2011;12:1126-36.
- [28] Giordano C, Albani D, Gloria A, Tunesi M, Batelli S, Russo T, et al. Multidisciplinary perspectives for Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases: hydrogels for protein delivery and cell-based drug delivery as therapeutic strategies. *Int J Artif Organs* 2009;32:836-50.
- [29] Nair S, Remya NS, Remya S, Nair PD. A biodegradable in situ injectable hydrogel based on chitosan and oxidized hyaluronic acid for tissue engineering applications. *Carbohydr Polym* 2011;85:838-44.

- [30] Zhang R, Xue M, Yang J, Tan T. A novel injectable and In Situ crosslinked hydrogel based on hyaluronic acid and α,β -polyaspartylhydrazide. *J Appl Polym Sci* 2012;125:1116-26.
- [31] Lu C, Wang X, Wu G, Wang J, Wang Y, Gao H, et al. An injectable and biodegradable hydrogel based on poly(α,β -aspartic acid) derivatives for localized drug delivery. *J Biomed Mater Res, Part A* 2014;102A:628-38.
- [32] Peng Q, Sun X, Gong T, Wu CY, Zhang T, Tan J, et al. Injectable and biodegradable thermosensitive hydrogels loaded with PHBHHx nanoparticles for the sustained and controlled release of insulin. *Acta Biomater* 2013;9:5063-9.
- [33] Fu S, Ni P, Wang B, Chu B, Zheng L, Luo F, et al. Injectable and thermo-sensitive PEG-PCL-PEG copolymer/collagen/n-HA hydrogel composite for guided bone regeneration. *Biomaterials* 2012;33:4801-9.
- [34] Thornton AJ, Alsberg E, Hill EE, Mooney DJ. Shape retaining injectable hydrogels for minimally invasive bulking. *J Urol* 2004;172:763-8.
- [35] Cameron NR. High internal phase emulsion templating as a route to well-defined porous polymers. *Polymer* 2005;46:1439-49.
- [36] Fuoco C, Salvatori ML, Biondo A, Shapira-Schweitzer K, Santoleri S, Antonini S, et al. Injectable polyethylene glycol-fibrinogen hydrogel adjuvant improves survival and differentiation of transplanted mesoangioblasts in acute and chronic skeletal-muscle degeneration. *Skeletal Muscle* 2012;2:24.
- [37] Habib M, Shapira-Schweitzer K, Caspi O, Gepstein A, Arbel G, Aronson D, et al. A combined cell therapy and in-situ tissue-engineering approach for myocardial repair. *Biomaterials* 2011;32:7514-23.
- [38] Frisman I, Seliktar D, Bianco-Peled H. Nanostructuring of PEG-fibrinogen polymeric scaffolds. *Acta Biomater* 2010;6:2518-24.
- [39] Yom-Tov O, Seliktar D, Bianco-Peled H. Cell morphology in injectable nanostructured biosynthetic hydrogels. *J Biomed Mater Res Part A* 2014:n/a-n/a.
- [40] Zhang R, Ma PX. Poly(α -hydroxy acids)/hydroxyapatite porous composites for bone-tissue engineering. I. Preparation and morphology. *J Biomed Mater Res* 1999;44:446-55.
- [41] Krupa I, Nedelcev T, Racko D, Lacik I. Mechanical properties of silica hydrogels prepared and aged at physiological conditions: testing in the compression mode. *J Sol-Gel Sci Technol* 2010;53:107-14.
- [42] Layne DS, Marrian GF. Isolation of 16 β -hydroxyestrone and 16-oxo-17 β -estradiol from the urine of pregnant women. *Biochem J* 1958;70:244-8.
- [43] Tov OY, Luvitch S, Bianco-Peled H. Molecularly imprinted hydrogel displaying reduced non-specific binding and improved protein recognition. *J Sep Sci* 2010;33:1673-81.
- [44] Kim C, Lee KS, Kim YE, Lee K-J, Lee SH, Kim TS, et al. Rapid exchange of oil-phase in microencapsulation chip to enhance cell viability. *Lab Chip* 2009;9:1294-7.
- [45] Silva R, Ferreira H, Vasconcelos A, Gomes AC, Cavaco-Paulo A. Sonochemical proteinaceous microspheres for wound healing. *Adv Exp Med Biol* 2012;733:155-64.
- [46] Marino DJ. Evaluation of Pluronic Polyol F127 as a vehicle for petroleum hydrocarbons in the Salmonella/microsomal assay. *Environ Mutagen* 1987;9:307-16.
- [47] Salerno A, Borzacchiello R, Netti PA. Pore structure and swelling behavior of porous hydrogels prepared via a thermal reverse-casting technique. *J Appl Polym Sci* 2011;122:3651-60.
- [48] Dubruel P, Unger R, Van Vlierberghe S, Cnudde V, Jacobs PJS, Schacht E, et al. Porous Gelatin Hydrogels: 2. In Vitro Cell Interaction Study. *Biomacromolecules* 2007;8:338-44.
- [49] Leach JB, Schmidt CE. Characterization of protein release from photocrosslinkable hyaluronic acid-polyethylene glycol hydrogel tissue engineering scaffolds. *Biomaterials* 2004;26:125-35.
- [50] Brazel CS, Peppas NA. Modeling of drug release from swellable polymers. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm* 2000;49:47-58.

- [51] Levesque SG, Lim RM, Shoichet MS. Macroporous interconnected dextran scaffolds of controlled porosity for tissue-engineering applications. *Biomaterials* 2005;26:7436-46.
- [52] Mattisson C, Roger P, Jonsson B, Axelsson A, Zacchi G. Diffusion of lysozyme in gels and liquids. A general approach for the determination of diffusion coefficients using holographic laser interferometry. *J Chromatogr B: Biomed Sci Appl* 2000;743:151-67.
- [53] Han JH, Krochta JM, Hsieh Y-L, Kurth MJ. Mechanism and Characteristics of Protein Release from Lactitol-Based Cross-linked Hydrogel. *J Agric Food Chem* 2000;48:5658-65.
- [54] Dorkoosh FA, Coos Verhoef J, Ambagts MHC, Rafiee-Tehrani M, Borchard G, Junginger HE. Peroral delivery systems based on superporous hydrogel polymers: release characteristics for the peptide drugs buserelin, octreotide and insulin. *Eur J Pharm Sci* 2002;15:433-9.
- [55] Pis'men LM. Diffusion in porous media of a random structure. *Chem Eng Sci* 1974;29:1227-36.